

Spectrophotometric Studies of Transition Metal Complexes with 5-Hydroxy-8-quinolinecarboxylic Acid

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5-Hydroxy-8-quinolinecarboxylic acid forms coloured complexes with Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) ions in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture in the pH range 3.50 to 5.70. Spectral data show the formation of only 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complexes. The optimum ranges, molar absorptivities and photometric sensitivities have been established. The stepwise and overall stability constants for these metal complexes have been determined at 30° and 0.10 M ionic strength adopting the graphical extrapolation methods of Leden and Yatsimirskii. The log β_n values are further verified employing the Harvey and Manning technique.

QUINOLINECARBOXYLIC acids and their various substituted derivatives exhibit fungicidal, insecticidal, antibacterial and related activities^{1,2} and are widely used in qualitative, quantitative and spectrophotometric analyses of metal ions^{3,4}. 5-Hydroxy-8-quinolinecarboxylic acid (5OH8Q), which gave dark green colour with Fe(II) and blue-black with Ru(III) ions, was developed by Breckenridge and Singer⁵ as one of the most powerful colorimetric reagent for quantitative estimation of ruthenium (1×10^{-6} g/50 ml). Furthermore, this reagent was found to produce intense colour or precipitate with many transition and non-transition metal ions. Notwithstanding all these, the complex forming tendency of the reagent in solution has not been investigated so far. We, therefore, undertook a systematic study to determine the formation constants of the complexes formed from 5OH8Q and Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture at 30° and 0.10 M ionic strength at appropriate pH values, employing the graphical extrapolation methods of Leden⁶ and Yatsimirskii^{7,8} with necessary modifications⁹. At lower ethanol concentrations the copper complex precipitates out after several hr. The degrees of dissociation and hence the overall formation constants of these metal complexes have also been evaluated by Harvey and Manning method¹⁰.

Experimental

5-Hydroxy-8-quinolinecarboxylic acid was synthesized by known method⁵ and was purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol. Its purity was checked on the basis of its spectrum, elemental analysis and m.p. (225-226° with partial sublimation; lit. 226° decomposition with partial sublimation). Standard reagent solutions of desired strength in absolute ethanol were used. Metal perchlorate solutions were prepared and standardized as described earlier^{11,12}. Sodium perchlorate was

used as the supporting electrolyte for maintaining the ionic strength constant (0.10 M). The pH were adjusted with either perchloric acid or sodium hydroxide solutions using an Elico pH meter, LI-10T, with a combined glass and calomel electrodes. Other chemicals and solvents used in the spectrophotometric measurements were G.R. or of spectrograde quality. Experiments were carried out on a Beckmann DB manual spectrophotometer with quartz cells of one cm light path. The test solutions were thermostated at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and oxygen-free pre-saturated nitrogen gas was bubbled continuously before recording the absorbances.

Absorbance curves :

Absorption measurements of solutions containing metal ions and 5OH8Q in the 1 : 5 ratio showed maximum absorptions at 420, 430, 385, 420 and 390 nm for Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes, respectively, while 5OH8Q exhibited λ_{max} at 400 nm. The absorbance values for these complexes remained unchanged for a few days indicating their stability. A study of the dependence of colour intensity on pH of the complexing solutions revealed that maximum absorptions occurred at pH 3.50 for Fe(II), pH 4.00 for Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and pH 5.70 for Zn(II) systems.

Beer's law ranges, molar absorptivities and sensitivities :

Lambert-Beer's law was verified by measuring the absorptions of the solutions containing an excess of 5OH8Q (1.00×10^{-4} or 2.00×10^{-4} M) and varying amounts of Fe(II), Co(II), Cu(II) (0.25×10^{-5} to 2.00×10^{-5} M) or Ni(II), Zn(II) (0.50×10^{-5} to 4.00×10^{-5} M). These Beer's law plots, at a later stage, were used to calculate the concentrations of the metal complexes required in the graphical extrapolation methods. The molar absorptivities of the metal complexes as calculated from the Beer's law data were found to be 3000, 20000, 7000, 14000 and 4500 litres mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II),

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF METAL-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS BY LEDEN'S AND YATSIMIRSKII'S METHODS IN 50% (v/v) ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURE
Temp. 30°; $\mu = 0.10 M (NaClO_4)$

Ledén's Method				Yatsimirskii's Method										
[Total ligand] (moles/litre) $\times 10^5$	Absorbance	[Metal complexed] (moles/litre) $\times 10^5$	[Free metal] (moles/litre) $\times 10^5$	[L ⁻] (moles/litre) $\times 10^5$	Degree of complex formation (ϕ)	$\psi_1 \times 10^{-14}$	$\psi_2 \times 10^{-14}$	log ϕ	log $\frac{[L^-]}{[L^-] + 10}$	Mean molar extinction coefficient $(\bar{\epsilon}) \times 10^{-3}$	$f_1 \times 10^{-11}$	$f_2 \times 10^{-10}$	Y $\times 10^{-5}$	g $\times 10^6$
0.50	0.003	0.02	1.98	0.3654	1.0101	2.7641	—	0.004	0.563	0.150	4.1052	—	—	—
1.00	0.009	0.05	1.95	0.7149	1.0256	3.5810	—	0.011	0.854	0.450	6.2946	0.9867	—	1.9940
1.50	0.012	0.07	1.93	1.0808	1.0368	3.9603	—	0.016	1.094	0.600	5.5541	1.3884	9.9568	1.9445
2.00	0.015	0.10	1.90	1.4298	1.0526	3.6788	—	0.022	1.155	0.750	5.2455	1.9270	6.9940	2.3591
2.50	0.018	0.13	1.87	1.7793	1.0695	3.9060	—	0.029	1.250	0.900	5.0582	1.0913	5.5202	2.6689
3.00	0.022	0.14	1.86	2.1606	1.0753	3.4851	3.9851	0.032	1.335	1.100	5.0912	0.9884	4.6284	2.8087
3.50	0.025	0.16	1.84	2.5260	1.0869	3.4444	1.7419	0.036	1.402	1.250	4.9486	0.8121	3.9589	2.9048
4.00	0.028	0.19	1.81	2.8755	1.1050	3.6515	3.7463	0.043	1.459	1.400	4.8687	0.7412	3.4777	2.8754
4.50	0.031	0.21	1.79	3.2409	1.1178	3.6193	6.7666	0.048	1.511	1.550	4.7826	0.6842	3.0856	2.7547
5.00	0.034	0.24	1.76	3.5904	1.1364	3.7990	11.1129	0.056	1.555	1.700	4.7348	0.6309	2.7608	2.5354

Fe(II)-5OH8Q system
Total metal ion conc. = $3.00 \times 10^{-5} M$; $\phi H = 3.50$; $\phi K_3 = 7.60$; $\lambda_{max} = 430 \text{ nm}$; $HL = 50H8Q$

TABLE 2—THE VALUES OF DIFFERENT INTERCEPTS OF 5OH8Q-METAL COMPLEXES IN 50% (v/v) ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURE
 Temp. 30°; $\mu=0.10 M$ (NaClO₄)

Metal ion	Intercepts						
	a_1	a_2	$b_1=e_1$	b_2	c_1	c_2	e_2
Fe(II)	7.00×10^{11}	-2.00×10^{10}	2400	-3.70×10^{-6}	3.40×10^7	6.00×10^{14}	2360
Co(II)	2.96×10^{12}	-4.00×10^{10}	19000	-5.60×10^{-6}	8.50×10^7	1.50×10^{16}	17077
Ni(II)	3.85×10^{11}	-2.40×10^{10}	5500	-3.60×10^{-6}	3.45×10^7	1.40×10^{14}	5034
Cu(II)	2.60×10^{12}	-5.00×10^{10}	12000	-3.20×10^{-6}	1.40×10^8	2.00×10^{16}	10400
Zn(II)	9.20×10^9	-1.80×10^{10}	3700	-6.60×10^{-6}	1.52×10^8	1.00×10^{13}	2985

Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes, respectively and corresponding spectrophotometric sensitivities according to Sandell¹³ were obtained as 0.20, 3.80, 19.00, 8.00 and 25.00 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$.

Composition and stability constants of the complexes :

In both the (Job's¹⁴ and mole-ratio¹⁵) methods, equimolecular concentration [$2.00 \times 10^{-4} M$ for Fe(II), Co(II) and Cu(II) and $4.00 \times 10^{-4} M$ for Ni(II) and Zn(II) complexes] of the reactants in a constant volume of 25.00 ml were employed for studying the composition of these complexes. These stoichiometric studies revealed that the complexes are binary (1 : 2, M : L) in nature.

Stability constants of the complexes were determined by adopting the extrapolation methods of Leden⁶ and Yatsimirskii^{7,8}. The experimental part consisted of the measurement of the absorption of the solutions containing a constant amount of a metal ion and varying amounts of the ligand $\{[\text{Fe(II)}]=[\text{Co(II)}]=[\text{Cu(II)}]=2.00 \times 10^{-5} M, [5\text{OH8Q}]=0.50 \times 10^{-5}$ to $5.00 \times 10^{-5} M; [\text{Ni(II)}]=[\text{Zn(II)}]=4.00 \times 10^{-5} M, [5\text{OH8Q}]=1.00 \times 10^{-5}$ to $1.00 \times 10^{-4} M\}$ against the reagent as blank. The concentrations of the complexes formed were computed from the appropriate calibration curves¹⁶.

The overall stability constants of the complexes were also calculated using Harvey and Manning technique¹⁰ by considering the degree of dissociation (α) of the complexes formed.

Results and Discussion

The values of all the secondary concentration variables e.g., \bar{e} , ϕ , $[L]$ and $[M]$ and that of the different subsidiary functions, ψ_1, ψ_2, f_1, f_2 and g employed for the evaluation of stepwise formation constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of the complexes ML_1^+ and ML_2 respectively $[M=\text{Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II)}; L=5\text{OH8Q}]$ have been calculated from the pre-knowledge of mole-ratio and Beer's law data. Since the details of calculations for all the metal ions studied are similar, the data for Fe(II)-5OH8Q is presented in Table 1. The plots of the functions ψ_1 and ψ_2 vs $[L^-]$ (figures omitted to avoid duplication of data) gave linear relationships. On the other hand f_1, f_2 vs $[L^-]$ and \bar{e}, g vs Y plots were found to be curved in nature. A few experimental points, particularly near $[L^-] \rightarrow 0$ are scattered

from the usual lines. It might be due to low absorbance values as $[L^-]$ tends to zero and inherent experimental error that might be introduced in recording these data. However, it was observed that no significant error was introduced in plotting the best lines or curves and in measuring their intercepts on extrapolation. The values of different intercepts and that of e_1 and e_2 obtained are given in Table 2.

The values of metal-ligand stability constants obtained by the methods of Leden, Yatsimirskii and Harvey-Manning (Table 3) agree with each other. The small differences between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$

 TABLE 3—STEPWISE AND OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 5OH8Q-METAL COMPLEXES IN 50% (v/v) ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURE
 Temp. 30°; $\mu=0.10 M$ (NaClO₄)

Metal ion	Stability constant	Leden's method			Yatsimirskii's method		Harvey-Manning's method	
		method	method	method	method	method	method	
Fe(II)	$\log K_1$	8.10	8.47	—	—	—	—	
	$\log K_2$	7.25	7.02	—	—	—	—	
	$\log \beta_2$	15.35	15.49	15.42	—	—	—	
Co(II)	$\log K_1$	7.98	8.24	—	—	—	—	
	$\log K_2$	7.40	7.53	—	—	—	—	
	$\log \beta_2$	15.38	15.77	15.60	—	—	—	
Ni(II)	$\log K_1$	7.68	7.88	—	—	—	—	
	$\log K_2$	6.82	7.02	—	—	—	—	
	$\log \beta_2$	14.50	14.90	14.80	—	—	—	
Cu(II)	$\log K_1$	8.25	8.40	—	—	—	—	
	$\log K_2$	7.46	7.70	—	—	—	—	
	$\log \beta_2$	15.71	16.10	15.97	—	—	—	
Zn(II)	$\log K_1$	6.28	6.64	—	—	—	—	
	$\log K_2$	5.82	5.91	—	—	—	—	
	$\log \beta_2$	12.10	12.97	12.20	—	—	—	

The limit of error is ± 0.10 .

values indicate that *mono-* and *bis-* complexes are formed simultaneously in solution. In almost all the systems studied the values of molar extinction coefficients obtained from Beer's law show a close resemblance with the e_2 values obtained by Yatsimirskii's method.

The overall stability constants ($\log \beta_2$) of these metal complexes follow the order Fe(II) < Co(II) > Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II). Except for the stabilities of Fe(II) and Co(II) chelates, this sequence is in accordance with the Irving-Williams order¹⁷. This order is particularly important because it is valid

for most oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands irrespective of the structure of the ligand. The abnormally high stability of Fe(II) chelate has, however, been observed in many other structurally similar compounds, particularly with aromatic ligands e.g., riboflavin, folic acid¹⁹, *o*-phenanthroline¹⁹ and others²⁰. It has been attributed to the resonance stabilization energy of Fe(II) complex upon coordination with a ligand having an aromatic ring system¹⁹. Oxidation of Fe(II) to Fe(III) could not have occurred during the experiments which were performed strictly in an inert atmosphere. The greater log β_2 value for Ni(II) chelate over Zn(II) indicates that 5-hydroxy-8-quinolinecarboxylic acid, like other quinolinecarboxylic acids²¹ and their various substituted derivatives²² form inner complex compounds, i.e. behave as a strong field ligand. This is to be expected since nitrogen donors are usually σ -donors and produce a strong field. This indirectly proves that 5OH8Q, wherein no steric hindrance occurs due to the hydroxyl substituent, contains the metal ions linked to both sides by nitrogen and oxygen atoms of the same molecule i.e. bidentate chelates are formed. The possible involvement of the hydroxyl group at the distant 5th position in complexation is also over-ruled by conducting similar colour experiments with structurally related compounds like α -naphthol and 5-hydroxyquinoline²³ which do not develop any colour with these bivalent transition metal ions under the conditions studied. Moreover, dissociation of the hydroxyl proton takes place above pH 10; metal ions do not interact with it at lower pH where all the experiments were performed. A marginal increase in the stability constant value of Co(II)-5OH8Q chelate may be attributed to the additional energy due to Jahn-Teller distortion that occurs in such strong field ligands²⁴. Oxidation of Co(II) to Co(III) is again not feasible because absorption measurements were performed in sufficiently acidic medium and under inert atmosphere²⁵.

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